

Application of VIS and Land Change Modelers in Characterizing and Predicting the Urban Land Use/Cover Dynamics of Nnewi Metropolis, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Based on a sub-pixel approach, this study analysed the Land Use/Cover (LU/C) dynamics of Nnewi Metropolis in Anambra State, Nigeria. Landsat TM/ETM+ satellite imageries of 1986, 2001 and 2016 were characterized into different LU/Cs using Ridd's Vegetation, Impervious Surface, Soil and Water (VIS-W) model via Linear Spectral Mixture Analysis (LSMA). LU/C endmember fractions obtained were hardened to produce the final LU/C maps of the study area, per epoch. Cellular Automata Markov (Ca-Markov) chain and the Land Change Modeler (LCM) were used to predict future LU/C for the year 2031 and the transition of each LU/C categories between 2016 and 2031, respectively. ArcGIS 10.5, Idrisi Selva and Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS 22) were used to perform the analyses. The result of the classification yielded a high level of accuracy (Kappa coefficient >0.85) and revealed that vegetation reduced over the years; impervious surface increased exposed soil fractions reduced while water cover fluctuated throughout the study epoch. Change detection analyses showed that the magnitude of change for each LU/C category were highest in recent period (2001 – 2016), while the result of the Markov chain analysis revealed continued change, especially in the reduction of vegetated areas (-36.85sq.km) and water surfaces (-0.65sq.km) as well as in the proliferation of impervious surfaces (14.86sq.km) and soil fractions (22.63sq.km) in the year 2031. Furthermore, the application of LCM revealed all the LU/C transition categories, earmarking about 29sq.km of vegetal cover to be converted to impervious surfaces. The result of the Chi-square analysis however revealed that the predicted changes in LU/C categories for 2031 were statistically significant ($\alpha= 0.01$). Thus, this study is to serve as an objective base for environmental managers and planners to trace, model and simulate the implication of the rapid dynamics of urban landscapes from a continuous perspective, particularly when other geographical phenomena are to be better understood. It is also recommended that government and environmental managers are to roll-out phased programmes to track and manage the changing landscape or to revamp the current LU/C change scenario in Nnewi by making use of the LU/C transition map presented in this study.

Key words: Linear spectral mixture, sub-pixel, land change modeler, endmember.

Introduction

Driven by man's spatial decision, urbanization is currently modifying every sphere of life and remains a global force to be reckoned with, especially because it is human-centred, human-driven and human-dominated. According to Trivedi, *et al.* (2008), urbanization is now driving the economy of most nations; causing more nations to yearn for increased urbanization. Otherwise known as urban drift, urbanization is a process of shift from rural to urban areas in which an increasing proportion of an entire population lives in cities as well as suburb of cities (Nnebue, *et al.*, 2014). Over the years, the rate of urbanization in developing countries, and particularly Nigeria, has been noted for its spontaneity, and its effect on land use/cover (LU/C).

In Nigeria, the rate of population growth has been spectacular, moving from a growth rate of about 2.8% to 5.8% per annum, with more than 60% of her population projected to reside in urban centres by year 2025 (Alkali, 2005). Consequently, upon the increase of the population of urban areas, the urban landscapes have been modified as a result of factors such as loss of agricultural or primary forested lands and grasslands coupled with growing impervious surfaces such as roads, sidewalks, parking lots, rooftops, etc. which have grave implications. Research has shown that surface radiant temperature response is a function of varying surface cover which is more complex in urban areas than in rural settings due to the varying land uses or surface cover: vegetation, soil, impervious surface and water (Owen, *et al.*, 1998; Weng *et al.* 2006; and Ahmed, *et al.*, 2013a).

Anambra State is one of the states in Nigeria experiencing sporadic urbanization, especially in Awka, Onitsha and Nnewi which are noted as the mid-cities of the state based on their level of urbanization ever since the State was created in 1991, causing stress to the environment and the weakening of her ecosystem services (UN-Habitat, 2009). Meanwhile, with a growth rate of 2.21% per annum, with 60% of her population residing in urban centres and noted as the third (3rd) most urbanized state in Nigeria, Anambra State has been experiencing rapid population increase and attendant urban expansion at the detriment of the environment, available infrastructure, utilities and stress on other ecosystem services. It has been noted by Balogun, *et al.* (2011) that such stress is usually caused by unchecked and/or unplanned land transformation and has been asserted to be one of the most important fields of human-induced environmental transformation. It can, however, be expected that with such increases in population sizes, much land has been – and still will be – converted and as such demands (close) monitoring, especially in the three (3) most urbanized towns in the State: Awka, Onitsha and Nnewi (UN-HABITAT, 2009; Ifeka & Akinbobola, 2015).

The adoption of Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information System (GIS) has proved helpful in most studies of land use/cover classification but apart from the mere use of such tools, there is a need to internalize efforts in deploying more quantitative basis in understanding urban landscape dynamics. Therefore, the V-I-S model, as proposed by Ridd (1995) was adopted in this study. The V-I-S model was however used to study the heterogeneity or morphology of the urban landscape of Salt Lake City Metropolitan area, by examining satellite images and aerial photographs. Proposed as a fundamental theory, the V-I-S model was developed to simplify the quantification of different surface components which are not often times orthometrically or spatially separated in satellite imageries (Hung, 2002; Zemba, 2010). The central idea of the model can be visualized in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The V-I-S model
 Source: Ridd (1995)

From Figure 1, each axis represents one component: vegetation, impervious surface and soil. Taking a medium-density residential area as seen in the aforementioned diagram is an illustration of an area characterized by 40% impervious surface, 45% vegetal cover and 15% soil. This simplification can however be complicated as Zemba (2010) observed, that each LU/C type can possibly appear, not as a point in the diagram but as a range of values. This is to say, features or pixels can be shown as a set of combination of V-I-S components within certain threshold. Thus, it has been recognized that the spatial, varying character of LU/C as shown in the study of Ridd (1995) can be better described by probability surfaces (Zhan, *et al.*, 2000).

In other words, each pixel is allowed to have a “class member” probability rather than a (generalized) single class label and the result of this operation has been successfully utilized by many authors (Small, 2001; Rasheet, *et al.*, 2001; Lu & Weng, 2004; Eastman, 2012; Feizizadeh & Blaschke, 2013) and particularly by Abubakar (2013) who included water fractions, making it VIS-Water model. Hence, upon this premise, this study adopted a quantitative

approach to characterize and simulate land cover components, such that could aid in understanding the dynamics of urbanization on one hand and in the modelling of different environmental phenomena in Nnewi.

Study Area

Anambra State is one of the 36 states of Nigeria, created on 27th August 1991. It is absolutely located on Latitudes 5° 47' N and 6° 48' N, and Longitudes 6° 38' E and 7° 21' E. See Figure 2. According to UN-Habitat (2009), there are seven urban areas recognized by the Anambra State Government, namely: Awka, Onitsha, Nnewi, Ihiala, Ekwulobia, Otuocha and Ogidi. Thus, out of the seven (7) urban areas, this study focused rather on the State's industrial nerve, Nnewi, which also happens to be the second largest city in Anambra South Senatorial Zone of the state (Orji & Obasi, 2012). Nnewi Metropolis comprises part of Nnewi North, Nnewi South, Ekwusigo and Idemili South LGAs. As shown in Figure 2, the core urban area of Nnewi lies about 25km south of Onitsha between Latitudes 5°58'N and 6°05'N and Longitudes 6°55' E and 7°00'E, covering an area of 72.52km² (Phil-Eze, 2010). Nnewi is bounded in the north by Nnobi, to the south by Utuh, east by Amichi and to the west by Ojoto, although for this study, a 225sq.km grid was used to delineate the Nnewi Metropolis as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Nigeria showing Anambra State (top) and Anambra State showing the study area, Nnewi (bottom)

The area has been said to be experiencing rapid population increase, particularly in Nnewi North and Nnewi South LGAs alone, with a population estimated by the Anambra State Bureau of Statistics (2011) to be about 460,000 persons in 2011 and have be forecasted in this study to be above 520,000 in just five (5) years, 2016, as shown in Figure 3. Logically, in the next fifteen (15) years, i.e. 2031, more than 200,000 persons will be added to this figure,

which excludes migrant population who visit the region for commercial purposes or for other ancillary activities. Generally, the city, together with its satellite towns spans over 1,076.9 square miles (2,789 km²) is a home to nearly 2.5 million residents as at 2005 in Anambra State (Wikipedia, 2016).

Figure 3: Population graphical estimation of Nnewi North and South L.G.As
 Source: Adapted and modified from Anambra State Bureau of Statistics (2007 – 2011)

Meanwhile, land use within Nnewi is rather not orderly and varies between residential, commercial, industrial and agricultural types with each type dominating according to the perceived interest of the landowners. Nnewi’s residential land use makes up about 42% of the land use/cover, with a little above 10% making up areas for commerce and industrial activities. Meanwhile, vegetated areas (i.e. agriculture/wood land) occupy only about 16% of the total land use of Nnewi (UN-Habitat, 2009). As such, there is every tendency that the proportion of land use in Nnewi reflects that of a typical traditional (Igbo) setting which is characterized with a commercial centre, ample open space for recreation, religious, economic and socio-cultural activities as well. However, this varying and changing land use types in urban centres in the State, according to many authors (Olajoke, 2007; Opoko & Oluwatayo, 2014; Musa, *et al.*, 2014; Ifatimehin, *et al.*, 2015; Ifatimehin, *et al.*, 2016; etc.), have varying impacts on different urban phenomena: utilities and infrastructure; change in green space per capita, micro-climate, crime, etc. which must be clearly understood without (much) generalization. Thus, these modifications, no matter their scales, magnitude or sizes ought to be analysed objectively to aid environmental managers in building sustainable cities, both in Nnewi and beyond.

Materials and Methods

The study adopted both experimental and survey designs to achieve its set objectives. As a study which deployed geospatial technologies, the experimental design involved the acquisition, processing and analyses of (remotely sensed) satellite imageries in a Geographic Information System (GIS) laboratory. On the other hand, the survey design employed in this study was for groundtruthing and/or validation of the classification results obtained in the study. See Figure 4 for the complete workflow utilized in this study. Meanwhile, medium resolution Landsat 4, 7 and 8 satellite imageries of 1986, 2001 and 2016 covering the study area, respectively, were downloaded online from the official website of the United States Geologic Survey (USGS) Earth Resources Observation Systems Data Centre (<http://www.glovis.usgs.gov>). The Landsat images were selected, based on availability, from Landsat Archives in Path 189/Row 56 for summer months - to maintain seasonal consistency. See Table 1 for details.

Table 1: Details of satellite image scenes used in the study

Satellite Date of Acquisition	Satellite Sensor	Bands	Resolution (m)
21/12/1986	Landsat 4 Thematic Mapper (TM)	2-5,7	30
09/01/2001	Landsat 7 Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM+)	2-5,7	30
15/03/2016	Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS	2-7	30

Figure 4: Workflow of the study

ArcGIS 10.5 and IDRISI Selva software were used to perform various digital image pre-processing, processing and analyses to achieve the set research objectives. For example, errors such as atmospheric haze, image stripes (caused by variable detector output), etc. were all removed to ensure the use of highly accurate data for analysis. Thus, to achieve the set objectives of the study, both soft and hard classification algorithms were used to characterize LU/C fractions in the selected study area.

First, all the acquired satellite imageries were pre-processed and separated into identifiable end-member classes from end-signatures and the LSMA which is based on the VIS-W model approach, hitherto discussed, was used to perform soft classification. The result obtained therefrom was then subjected to a supervised, hard classification method using the maximum likelihood algorithm. To this end, a broad LU/C classification scheme, characterized by materials that have (relatively) homogeneous spectral properties all over the images, was adopted. See Table 2 for the LU/C classification scheme and the studies of Onwuka, *et al.* (2017) and Musa, *et al.* (2017) for the analytical procedure for soft and hard classification presented in this study.

Table 2: Details of land use classification scheme adopted for the study

Land Use Type	Description
Impervious Area (I)	Also known as built-up area and comprises of all infrastructure – residential, commercial, mixed use and industrial areas, villages, settlements, road network, pavements, and man-made structures.
Water Body (W)	Comprises of river, permanent open water, lakes, ponds, canals, permanent/seasonal wetlands, low-lying area, marshy land and swamps
Vegetation (V)	Trees, natural vegetation, mixed forest, gardens, parks and playgrounds, grassland, vegetated lands, agricultural lands and crop fields
Soil (S)	Fallow land, earth and sand land in-filling, erosion sites, construction sites, developed land, excavation sites, open space, bare soils and the remaining land cover types.

Source : Ahmed, *et al.* (2013a)

The result of a single (hardened) LU/C map per epoch was obtained and the overall accuracy was assessed using the Kappa coefficient, based on a random selection of 250 reference pixels for each study year considered, as they were compared against the data obtained *in-situ* via GPS survey campaign. Note that the Kappa coefficient is a measure of the proportional (or percentage) improvement by the classifier over a purely random assignment to classes (Ahmed, *et al.*, 2013b). On the other hand, the user's accuracy measures the proportion of each land cover class, which is correct whereas producer's accuracy measures the proportion of the actual LU/C fraction obtained from the GPS survey campaign that are correctly classified.

Furthermore, the hardened VIS-W LU/C maps obtained for the most recent times, i.e. 2001 and 2016 were used to generate the Markov probability statistics which served as input in the Cellular Automata (CA-Markov) operation that was used to predict future LU/C for a future time, t_3 , i.e. 2031 (See Sahalu, 2014). Generally, in the Markovian process, it is assumed that the future state of a system in time t_2 can be predicted based on the immediate preceding state, time t_1 . Hence, according to Eastman (2012), if $X[k]$ is a Markov chain with the states $\{x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots\}$, then the probability of transition from the state i to the state j in one-time instant can be expressed as:

$$p_{i,j} = Pr(X[k+1] = j | X[k] = i) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

If Markov chain therefore has a finite number of states, i.e. n , transition probability matrix can still be defined viz:

$$\begin{bmatrix} P_{1,1} & P_{1,2} & \dots & P_{1,n} \\ P_{2,1} & P_{2,2} & \dots & P_{2,n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ P_{n,1} & P_{n,2} & \dots & P_{n,n} \end{bmatrix} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Hence, the Markov Chain model was used to produce related probability change matrices and then, the CA tool was used to consider the composition of associations of pixels, based on the concept of proximity (i.e. regions closer to existing areas of the same class will have a higher propensity to change to a different class) and then was used to project the future state of such cells. The CA model can however be expressed as follows:

$$S(t, t + 1) = f(S(t), N) \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

- Where S = set of limited and discrete cellular states
- N = the cellular field
- t and $t + 1$ = difference in times and
- f = transformation rule of cellular states in local space.

Thus, the hardened LU/C maps of 2001 and 2016 were used to first determine the different cell transition rules before applying a CA filter of 5 x 5 contiguity filter to predict LU/C for 2031. In addition, the Land Change Modeler (LCM) in Idrisi Selva software was used to map the transition areas of the LU/C categories and revealed individual conversion rates and future areas expected to be converted into other categories. The non-parametric Chi-square statistic was used to analyse the significance of the difference in LU/C fractions between 2016 and that predicted for 2031, while simple statistical charts, tables and graphs were used generally to present the findings of the study.

Results and Discussion

The result of the LSMA characterization of LU/C fractions for 1986, 2001 and 2016 are presented in Figure 5. From a sub-pixel perspective, the sub-maps range from 1 – 0, signifying the degree of membership or intensity of the different LU/C fractions (i.e. vegetation, impervious surface, soil and water) considered in the study. The vegetation end-member submaps reveal a gradual reduction in the intensity of vegetation over the years in Nnewi. High intensity vegetal composition appeared almost everywhere around the study area in 1986 but appears to be rather diminished and/or limited in 2016 to areas of riparian vegetation types or areas along stream courses. This is a clear indication of rapid deforestation taking place in the region as opined by UN-Habitat (2009) and Phil-Eze (2010). On the other hand, impervious surface increased in intensity and spatial dimension from 1986 to 2016. Apart from the city centre of Nnewi that appeared as purple (indicating high intensity of built-up fractions) in 2016, other surrounding areas for the same year appear to be modified – having moderate intensities of imperviousness. These two fractions: vegetation and impervious surface temporal modification is like that of Awka (Ifeka and Akinbobola, 2015; Musa, *et al.*, 2017) and again, has a way of affecting the LST of the region as suggested by Deosthali (2000), Harman (2003), and Falahatkar, *et al.* (2011). Also, high intensity soil members were revealed around the town but increased in number of patches/sites from 1986 to 2016. Area of high intensity soil end-member indicates areas where soils were/are exposed, such as (gully) erosion sites or newly cultivated farmlands, especially along the river at the northern flank of the region.

Figure 5: Result of LU/C endmember fractions derived from LSMA for 1986, 2001 and 2016

On the other hand, intensities of water end-member fractions were medium and scanty in 1986 and 2001 but appeared higher in 2016 at the North-eastern axis of Nnewi region. This finding is similar to that obtained in Awka where the streams in the region were mostly predominant under riparian forest formation, thereby making water pixels or fractions difficult to be registered by the satellite sensor but with deforestation, such water fractions became more exposed and evident. Thus, in order to categorize the LU/C fractions obtained from the LSMA to establish the trend and rate of urbanization in the town, the hardening operation was performed. The summarized result of the hardened (or categorized) multi-temporal LU/C classification of Nnewi is presented in Figure 6. Meanwhile, the overall accuracies of the classified images for the different epochs: 1986, 2001 and 2016 were, respectively, found to be 85.28%, 88.89%, and 93.44%, with Kappa coefficients of 0.85, 0.89, and 0.93 as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Accuracy assessment of LU/C categories obtained in the study

Year	User's Accuracy (%)				Producer's Accuracy (%)				Overall Accuracy (%)	Kappa Coefficient
	Veg.	Imp. Surface	Soil	Water	Veg.	Imp. Surface	Soil	Water		
1989	85.31	88.23	86.05	89.25	84.12	87.26	85.77	88.50	85.28	0.85
2001	90.42	89.76	89.26	92.23	86.30	88.97	88.19	91.23	88.89	0.89
2016	92.26	95.12	91.30	91.08	93.65	96.59	91.11	92.31	93.44	0.93

Figure 6: Hardened LU/C fractions of Nnewi from 1986 (top) to 2016 (bottom)

From Table 3, it is observed that the accuracy of the LU/C images tend to increase over time. This could be said to be due to the availability of more detailed correlation of more recent images with the GPS survey campaign data acquired *in-situ*. Generally, however, the result of the accuracy assessment indicates a good performance of the LSMA or the sub-pixel approach adopted in this study. The table showing the spatio-temporal dynamics of LU/C categories in Nnewi Metropolis.

Table 4: LU/C dynamics of Nnewi from 1986 - 2016

Land Use/Cover categories	Area (Sq.Km)			Change [2016-2001]		Change [2001-1986]		Total Change [2016-1986]	
	2016	2001	1986	Mag.	Freq.	Mag.	Freq.	Mag.	Freq.
Vegetation (V)	131.345	208.251	212.924	-76.906	-5.13	-4.673	-0.31	-81.579	-2.72
Impervious surface (I)	70.414	15.3279	5.921	55.086	3.67	9.407	0.63	64.493	2.15
Soil (S)	21.017	0.8883	5.456	20.129	1.34	-4.568	-0.30	15.561	0.52
Water (W)	2.224	0.5328	0.699	1.691	0.11	-0.167	-0.01	1.5246	0.05
Total	225	225	225						

As shown in the LU/C maps and Table 4, vegetation reduced over the years from 212.92sq.km (94.63%) in 1986 to 208.25sq.km (92.56%) in 2001 and reduced drastically to about 131.35sq.km (58.38%) in 2016. Impervious surface category on the contrary, increased from as low as 5.92sq.km (2.63%) in 1986 – before the creation of Anambra State, to about 15.33sq.km (6.81%) in 2001, and finally increased drastically to about 70.41sq.km (31.30%) in 2016. Exposed soil fractions accounted for an area of about 5.46sq.km (2.42%) in 1986, reduced to about 0.89sq.km (0.39%) in 2001 but increased sporadically to about 21.02sq.km (9.34%) in 2016. Meanwhile, water cover fluctuated during each study epoch; 0.70sq.km (0.31%) in 1986 to about 0.53sq.km (0.23%) in 2001 and increased to about 2.22sq.km (0.99%) in 2016. It can be deduced from the foregoing that there were drastic modifications in the landscape of Nnewi region between 2001 and 2016 than that experienced between 1986 and 2001. This is clearly depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Chart showing the LU/C dynamics of Nnewi from 1986 – 2016

Figure 7 shows a graphical result of the change detection analysis. It reveals clearly that vegetation had the highest magnitude of change of -31.03sq.km between 2001 and 2016 with an annual rate of change of -5.13sq.km per capita as against -0.31sq.km (31ha) between 1986 and 2001. Thus, a total of 81.58sq.km of vegetal cover was lost at an average rate of -2.7sq.km per year. Impervious surface category increased with a magnitude of 55.09sq.km at a rate of 3.67sq.km per year between 2001 and 2016 as against a magnitude of 9.41sq.km at 0.63sq.km per year between 1986 and 2001. Also, soil and water fractions experienced higher magnitudes of change of about 20.13sq.km and 1.69sq.km between 2001 and 2016, respectively. However, increase in water cover, soil and impervious surfaces as well as the massive reduction of vegetation, especially between 2001 and 2016 can be attributed to an increased rate of urbanization during the period as opined by Phil-Eze (2010) and Ifeka and Akinbobola (2015). Thus, given that the rapidity of LU/C modification has been heightened in recent times, it is expected that they will be huge implications on the landscape of Nnewi as this will affect access and availability of basic infrastructure (Njoku, *et al.*, 2010; Opoko and Oluwatayo, 2014), agricultural land depletion (Phil-Eze, 2010; Orji and Obasi, 2012; Musa, *et al.*, 2014), increase in flash floods and hydrology (Ifatimehin, *et al.*, 2012; Anukwonke, 2014), development and/or

exacerbation of the UHI effect (Yuan & Bauer, 2007; DeCarolis, 2012; Xie & Zhou, 2015) and the proliferation of hyperthermia diseases (Ifatimehin, *et al.*, 2015; Ifatimehin, *et al.*, 2016), etc.

As part of the objective of this study, the observed dynamics had to be predicted using the current Business As Usual (BAU) scenario (i.e. 2001 and 2016) for the year 2031. This was done by using the CA-Markov prediction tool in Idrisi Selva. The result of the Markov Chain probability matrix of Nnewi from 2016 to 2031 is shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Markov Chain probability matrix for Nnewi between 2016 and 2031

Given:	Probability of changing to			
	Vegetation	Impervious surface	Soil	Water
Vegetation	0.6178	0.2929	0.0789	0.0104
Impervious surface	0.1428	0.5987	0.2561	0.0024
Soil	0.0669	0.2067	0.7264	0.0000
Water	0.8429	0.1081	0.0135	0.0355

The result of the Markov chain analysis as presented above shows a high probability (0.62) of vegetal cover expected to persist from 2016 – 2031, with more probability of the same to be converted into impervious surfaces than other LU/C categories considered in the study. The probability of impervious surfaces to persist in 2031 is about 0.60 while there is a relatively high probability (0.26) for impervious surfaces to be converted to soil fractions (e.g. tarred road surfaces are likely to be converted to soils, etc.). There is also a high probability (0.74) for soil covers to remain the same or changed to impervious surface – with a relatively high probability of 0.2. Thus, for areas where soil fractions may be identified in the 2031 LU/C map of Nnewi, there is likelihood for them to be impervious in nature. Lastly, water bodies show a high probability to be retained in future (2031) or converted to impervious areas. The result of the Ca-Markov LU/C transition maps of 2031 for the study area is shown in Figure 8.

The LU/C transition map of Nnewi shows areas of serious modification: vegetation to soil (light grey) and vegetation to impervious surfaces (yellow). The map also shows areas of persistent vegetation and built-up areas (i.e. sites with no modification) from 2016 to 2031. Unlike the result obtained for Onitsha (Izueke & Eme, 2013; Onwuka, *et al.*, 2017) and Awka (Musa, *et al.*, 2017), it is however envisaged that there will be more pronounced modifications in LU/C categories in Nnewi, especially in the conversion of vegetated areas to bare soils and impervious surfaces. However, most of the vegetation–impervious surface modifications are envisaged to take place in and around present built-up areas as shown on the map. Table 6 presents a summary of the transition pattern that is predicted to occur for different LU/C categories in Nnewi between 2016 to 2031, while Figure 9 shows the predicted LU/C Map of Nnewi for 2031

From Table 6, it can be observed that the category of vegetation to impervious surface transition indicates a high rate of deforestation or devegetation in Nnewi, particularly as about 2sq.km of vegetated areas are predicted to be converted annually. As hitherto mentioned, this will have gross implication on forests, biodiversity, micro-climate, etc. The table also shows that no exposed soil fractions in 2016 will be converted into vegetation while the reverse will be the case. Another issue that raises concern also is the fact that about 13.95sq.km of impervious surfaces have been predicted to be converted to soil fractions. It means that parts of the impervious surfaces may be susceptible to the ravishing action of erosion as noted in the region by Orji and Obasi (2012).

Figure 8: LU/C transition map of Nnewi

Table 6: LU/C transition statistics of Nnewi between 2016 and 2031

S/No.	Land use transition categories	Area (Sq.km)	Annual Rate (Sq.km)
1	Persistent Vegetation	93.150	0
2	Impervious surface to vegetation	0.450	0.03
3	Soil to Vegetation	0.000	0
4	Water to Vegetation	0.900	0.06
5	Vegetation to Impervious surface	29.025	1.935
6	Persistent Impervious surface	55.800	0
7	Soil to Impervious surface	0.225	0.015
8	Water to Impervious surface	0.000	0
9	Vegetation to soil	9.000	0.6
10	Impervious surface to Soil	13.950	0.93
11	Persistent Soil	20.700	0
12	Water to Soil	0.000	0
13	Vegetation to Water	0.225	0.015
14	Impervious surface to Water	0.000	0
15	Soil to Water	0.000	0
16	Persistent Water	1.350	0
	Total	225	

This is a serious affair as this singular transition category can affect lives and properties situated at the identified locations. Moreover, other transition categories shown on the map have been captured in Table 6 but the general result of the predicted LU/C categories of 2031 for Nnewi region is given in Table 7.

Figure 9: LU/C predicted map of Nnewi (2031)

Table 7: LU/C categories of Nnewi between 2016 and 2031

S/No.	LU/C categories	2016	2031	Change [2031-2016]	
		Area (Sq.km)	Area (Sq.km)	Magnitude	Annual Frequency
1	Vegetation (V)	131.3451	94.500	-36.8451	-2.46
2	Impervious surface (I)	70.4142	85.275	14.8608	0.99
3	Soil (S)	21.0168	43.65	22.6332	1.51
4	Water (W)	2.2239	1.575	-0.6489	-0.04
	Total	225	225		

Table 7 above shows the areal coverage of the predicted LU/C category of Nnewi in 2031 and the level of deviation from the result obtained for 2016. Although, the Nnewi LU/C map of 2016 reveals serious modification in the regions landscape, the result of the LU/C prediction shows continued modification in all LU/C categories. Vegetation is envisaged to be reduced by about 2.46sq.km per year with a magnitude of change of -36.85sq.km; built-up areas is predicted to increase by 0.99sq.km (99ha) per year with a magnitude of 14.86sq.km; soil cover is put at 1.51sq.km per year given a magnitude of 22.63sq.km; and water cover is predicted to reduce by 0.04sq.km per year with a magnitude of -0.65sq.km. The net change in LU/C categories can be seen in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Net change in LU/C categories of Nnewi between 2016 and 2031

From the foregoing, it is obvious that most of the LU/C classes, apart from water fractions will undergo drastic modification: positively or negatively, but whether the changes revealed are significant or not, there was therefore need to ascertain this using the Chi-square statistical test. See Table 8.

Table 8: Result of Chi-square test

Study Area		Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Nnewi	Pearson Chi-Square	15.316 ^c	3	.002
	Likelihood Ratio	15.521	3	.001
	N of Valid Cases	450		

- a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 23.47.
- b. 2 cells (25.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.00.
- c. 2 cells (25.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.99.

The result of the Chi-square test reveals an asymptotic significant change ($p = 0.002$) in LU/C fractions as predicted for the year 2031. As such, it draws to mind that if the BAU scenario is maintained, the predictions made in this study will portend significant change in the urban landscape of Nnewi. Although, the driving agent or forces behind these modifications are not within the scope of this study, the study has been able to give insight on how they will occur and more particularly, mapped areas of such occurrences. Therefore, if a significant change in the LU/C of Nnewi has been predicted, it consequently means that other environmental phenomena (biodiversity, land degradation, climate, infrastructure, pollution, food security, etc.), as mentioned earlier will also be affected significantly in the area. This also is not far from the fact that the population of the area is on the increase as noted earlier also in this study.

Although LU/C of Nnewi Metropolis have not been studied from such a quantitative perspective, many studies (Ezeomodo & Igbokwe, 2013; Ifeka & Akinbobola, 2015; Musa, *et al.*, 2017; Onwuka, *et al.*, 2017; etc.) have established the spontaneity of urbanization in other towns in Anambra State. From visual inspection, one can easily observe the gradual development of the 'urban form' of Nnewi which is still expected to increase in future. This is at variance however with the findings of Onwuka, *et al.* (2017) who discovered stagnancy in the spatial growth of Onitsha, presently and in the future (2031). Hence, there is need for urban planners to understand the varying metamorphosis of different urban areas and their (ecological) footprints as they may not all exhibit the same character and influence on other environmental phenomena. For instance, Mallick (2014) have opined that the attendant conversion of greenery into impervious surfaces remains the principal cause of high surface temperature in urban areas. More so, the role of Nnewi as the industrial nerve of the city is expected not only to deviate from the pattern exhibited by Onitsha, Awka and other urban areas but also its rapidity is worth noting.

Conclusion and Recommendation

From the foregoing, this study was able to assess the rapidity of urbanization or the dynamics of LU/C fractions in Nnewi for different epochs (1986, 2001 and 2016) by utilizing a continuum, sub-pixel perspective in a GIS environment, which is different from the widely used, generalized classification approach. The approach of this study provides a more quantitative basis by which different environmental phenomena could be modelled or understood, objectively. It also deployed the use of different land modellers to reveal and predict the dynamics of LU/C fractions in Nnewi, the industrial hub of Anambra State. It has been revealed that the rapidity of LU/C modification is more pronounced in recent epoch (i.e. between 2001 and 2016) and translates into a statistically significant change in the coverage of each LU/C fractions in 2031 as predicted using the CA-Markov model. With the aid of the LCM, areas of rapid LU/C transitions were identified, quantified and mapped, thus, lays bare the need for the use of smart approaches in understanding the use and spatio-temporal dynamics of the urban landscape, particularly when land biophysical descriptors are to be considered. This will go a long way in mitigating the impacts occasioned by the unplanned modification of LU/C fractions which are already evident in most urban centres of the country, Nigeria.

We hereby recommend the following:

- that government rolls-out a phased programme(s) to revamp the current scenario in LU/C modification, particularly in adopting smart Green Policies and the provision of basic infrastructures, amenities and utilities in the suburbs in order to reduce in-migration in the study area and beyond;
- environmental managers should deploy the use of remote sensing and advanced GIS technologies in modelling environmental phenomena, especially as it has to do with understanding the chaotic landscape of urban areas.
- researchers and/or agencies responsible for combating the menace of (gully) erosion in Nnewi should focus more in unravelling areas where impervious surfaces may be predicted to be converted into soil fractions. This will help mostly in the prediction and early preparation of the incidence or occurrence of gullying in the region and beyond; and
- lastly, further research is expected to deepen the classification scheme used in this study to a more comprehensive one, particularly in areas where rock outcrops are prevalent, as well in other studies that depend on land resource data on a continuum-base.

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